

In the field of natural language processing, a part of the research is directed towards the improvement of systems that can model language. For a certain task, such as classifying the named entities (names, institutions, places, etc.) in a given document, practitioners race against each other to obtain state-of-the-art (SOTA) results. Self-proclaiming a model as SOTA comes with high responsibility as it indicates that, in terms of a chosen performance metric (such as accuracy or precision), the model makes the least errors. Usually, one or multiple benchmark datasets are used to compare models in the community. Naturally, one might want to reproduce any experiment that reported a performance score to assess the validity of their results.

Replication should be straightforward, but it is not: while the code can and should be easily downloadable, the hardware used is usually different across users and the installed software dependencies almost never aligned 1:1. Small pre-processing steps of the data, like removing outliers or shuffling the data, are sometimes not reported. Finally, it is improbable that the results can be reproduced to the exact score: the researcher decides what the margins of reproduction error should be.

In the light of these obstacles, a researcher is satisfied when they succeed in reproducing the reported results. But is being satisfied with reproduction a desirable behavior? And how many attempts should a researcher make to reproduce some results? As a variant of the positive results bias, in this (far from remote) scenario the researcher tunes the experimental settings (data, software, hardware) until their results coincide with previous studies.